

Development of a MEMS-Based Raman Spectrometer

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Abstract—This paper discusses the development of a Raman spectrometer incorporated into a MEMS device for use in environmental monitoring against chemical and biological agents. The current design incorporates a 1525 nm laser diode as an optical pump source, and a tunable Fabry-Pérot interferometer as the wavelength selection element.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the threat of airborne chemical and biological attacks grows, new methods of monitoring the environment against these agents are required. The difficulties inherent in effective environmental monitoring are numerous. Handheld detection equipment can provide accurate identification of chemical species, but this method requires both macroscopic quantities of analyte and trained personnel to collect and interpret data. “Bottom-up” approaches involving as-grown nanostructures can provide the requisite sensitivity, but can provide numerous false positives, while the devices themselves must either be replaced periodically or undergo a potentially long “reset time,” which can become expensive and defeats the purpose of an autonomous network [1-3].

SSC Pacific has designed and developed the technology to implement a micro electromechanical system (MEMS) based Raman spectrometer. The current design consists of diode laser excitation at 1525 nm, including a surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) substrate for signal enhancement and a commercial off-the-shelf InGaAs photodiode detector. The wavelength selection element is a Fabry-Pérot interferometer implemented on a MEMS positioning system. The interferometer design parameters are such that the spectrometer resolution is $\sim 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, rivaling handheld detection systems currently commercially available [4], while the form factor ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^3$) is small enough to deploy unobtrusively and *en masse* in areas where high contaminant concentrations would be present (*e.g.*, ventilation ducts).

II. FABRICATION AND ASSEMBLY

The fabrication of the MEMS Raman spectrometer was based a wafer level bonding process utilizing a Silicon-On-Insulator (SOI) wafer bonded to a bulk wafer using gold compression bonding. All fabrication steps were performed at Infotonics Technology Center (ITC) under government contract. Each wafer contained one of the two mirrors

comprising the Fabry-Perot cavity. The bottom wafer was a bulk n-type silicon wafer with resistivity of 5-20 Ohm-cm. A dielectric mirror was deposited on top of a sacrificial oxide that was grown on the surface of the wafer. The dielectric stack itself was comprised of three alternating layers of polysilicon and silicon dioxide which were tuned for a peak reflectivity for 1500 nm light. After deposition of the lower dielectric mirror aluminum metal electrodes were deposited and patterned followed by the lift-off of a Cr/Au layer for subsequent wafer to wafer gold compression bonding.

The upper wafer was an SOI wafer with n-type device layer resistivity of 0.1 – 1 Ohm-cm on top of a 500 nm Buried Oxide (BOX) layer. Fabrication of the upper mirror included etching arrays of openings in the device layer silicon where the mirrors would reside. This was accomplished using Potassium Hydroxide (KOH) with a patterned oxide hard mask. The etch was completed when all of the exposed silicon was etched down to the exposed BOX layer. At this point the hard mask oxide was removed and a new thermal oxide was re-grown which served as a sacrificial layer for the mirror deposition and patterning. The upper mirror dielectric layers were then deposited and patterned over the KOH etch windows as shown in Fig. 1a. Fig. 1b is a cross-sectional SEM image of the upper dielectric mirror stack comprised of three layers of polysilicon with two alternating layers of silicon dioxide deposited on a sacrificial thermal oxide and capped with a protective deposited oxide. Fig. 1c is an SEM image of the spring structure which surrounds the mirror array. The spring structure allows the entire mirror array to move in unison when an electrostatic potential is applied between the lower mirror electrodes and the device layer silicon of the upper mirror thus allowing for optical wavelength tuning of the cavity. After lift-off of Cr / Au on the upper wafer, the two wafers are ready for wafer level gold compression bonding. Fig. 1d is an IR transmission image through the assembled spectrometer, showing the mirror support structure, electrodes, bonding pads, and (faintly) the spring structure.

Once the wafers have been successfully bonded together at the wafer level, a window is etched through the backside of the lower mirror bulk wafer down to the lower mirror structure using Deep Reactive Ion Etching (DRIE). The sacrificial

Figure 1. (a) Deposition mask for the Fabry-Pérot mirror fabrication. (b) Cross-section of mirror showing Si/SiO₂ dielectric layers. (c) SEM image of spring for mirror displacement. (d) IR transmission through assembled interferometer, with opaque metallic electrodes.

oxide under the lower mirror is then plasma etched. The final step is to remove the handle wafer of the upper mirror using DRIE followed by removal of the BOX layer. The final structure is shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 below. Fig. 2 is a cross-sectional drawing of the completed sensor illustrating both upper and lower mirror dielectric stacks, lower mirror electrodes and gold compression bonding region. Fig. 3 is an IR image of the completed structure illustrating the alignment between the mirror array, springs, and electrodes.

Figure 2. Cross-sectional drawing of the fully fabricated MEMS Raman spectrometer.

The incorporation of the Fabry-Pérot interferometer into the overall device design is shown in Fig. 4. The laser impinges on a metal nanoparticle substrate designed for performing surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS), which increases the local electric field experienced by the adsorbed analyte molecules due to a coupling between the incident laser field and localized surface plasmons in the substrate. This in turn increases the Raman-scattered radiation; reported enhancement factors in the literature are typically on the order of 10^6 for ensemble averages, while

Figure 3. IR image of a completed spectrometer. A 4x4 array of upper mirrors is suspended above a single lower mirror using the suspension system shown in the image. Four electrodes are placed near the corners of each upper mirror support membrane to allow for electrostatic actuation and tuning of the optical cavity.

enhancements as high as 10^{14} have been reported for single molecule SERS [5]. Due to the laser excitation wavelength currently used (chosen for ease of prototype fabrication, silicon being transparent above $\sim 1\mu\text{m}$), as well as the nature of the analyte (minute airborne quantities of chemical or biological specimens), the SERS substrate is certainly advantageous, if not mandatory. The specific substrate chosen for the current generation of the probe is a film of high aspect ratio (20 nm diameter, 200 nm length) gold nanorods (Nanopartz, Inc.; 30-HAR-1400) deposited on a transparent silica substrate; a sample TEM image of the nanorods and a corresponding localized surface plasmon resonance spectrum is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 4. Schematic drawing of the assembled Chem-Bio sensor.

The Raman-scattered light is then collected by a collimating lens and directed through a laser line rejection filter (Omega Optical, XE1523), which provides an optical density of greater than 5.0 at the laser wavelength, while

providing ~85% transmission above the shoulder at ~1550 nm. The collimated light (the imperfect collimation arising from a finite source distribution and its effect on the interferometer transmission properties will be addressed below) then enters the Fabry-Pérot interferometer, where the transmitted wavelength will depend on the spacing between the mirrors (as previously mentioned, this spacing is varied by the application of a dc voltage to the interferometer electrodes). Finally, the transmitted light illuminates a commercial off-the-shelf InGaAs photodiode, producing a measurable photocurrent that, when correlated with applied voltage, yields the Raman spectrum.

Figure 5. LSPR spectrum (left) and TEM image (right) of HAR gold nanorods used as SERS substrate. Images courtesy Nanopartz, Inc. (www.nanopartz.com).

III. DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

The MEMS Raman spectrometer presents a number of interesting technical challenges that will be discussed below. The filter performance is a sensitive function of the input angle, which places constraints on the maximum resolution obtainable for a given range of input angles. Resolution performance requirements will then govern the acceptable angular incidence properties, which will in turn place limits on the form factor of the assembled spectrometer.

A. Fabry-Pérot Transmission vs. Angle

As was previously mentioned, the transmission properties of the Fabry-Pérot interferometer depend on the angle that the incident light rays make with the normal direction. The interferometer works by destructively interfering all rays whose wavelengths do not match the cavity spacing; as the angle relative to normal increases, the effective cavity spacing observed by the rays increases, and the transmission wavelength shifts.

The maximum obtainable resolution of the interferometer is thus limited by the angular spread of the light entering the interferometer. We see in Fig. 6 the calculated amplitude of the transmission wavelength vs. angle, using 7-layer dielectric mirrors with a cavity spacing of 12 μm , which is a typical mirror separation used in our interferometers. As can be seen, the transmission wavelength undergoes a dramatic shift as the angle increases. In order to calculate the effect of this spread on the interferometer resolution, we can model the transmission at a given angle as a function of wavelength and angle by a Gaussian lineshape of the form

$$f(\lambda, \theta) = A e^{(\lambda - \Lambda(\theta)/\sigma)^2}, \quad (1)$$

where A is a normalization constant, σ is determined by curve fitting to be ~0.3, and $\Lambda(\theta)$ is described by a second order polynomial,

$$\Lambda(\theta) = 1500 - 0.165 \theta^2. \quad (2)$$

The transmission function for any angle can then be calculated. In order to obtain the overall transmission function for an angular distribution up to some acceptance angle θ_c (determined by an aperture stop, usually the edge of the interferometer), we must integrate over all the possible angles (assuming a uniform angular distribution, see Fig. 7(a)):

$$f(\lambda) = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{\theta_c} \theta f(\lambda, \theta) d\theta d\phi, \quad (3)$$

where we have integrated over azimuthal angle ϕ , and the additional factor of θ corresponds to the Jacobian determinant for integration over polar coordinates.

Figure 6. (top) Plot of transmitted wavelength vs. angular deviation from normal incidence for the Fabry-Pérot interferometer. (bottom) Expansion of the boxed region.

In Fig. 7 (b-f) we show the overall transmission functions for a range of critical angles. At small angles the Gaussian transmission lineshape is preserved, whereas at larger angles the curve flattens out and takes more of a “boxcar” shape. The curves are all normalized to unit amplitude to facilitate comparison; naturally the larger the acceptance angle becomes, the stronger the observable signal will be. It is therefore advantageous to use the largest acceptance angle that does not possess detrimental characteristics for Raman

spectral identification – in the current system, these manifest primarily as increases in the linewidth – too broad a transmission function will not permit the resolution of closely spaced Raman vibrational modes.

Figure 7. (a) Surface of angular integration. (b-f) Overall transmission functions for increasing angular deviation

The best laboratory Raman instruments have resolutions of smaller than 1 cm^{-1} . Commercially available handheld systems are typically an order of magnitude larger, with resolutions approaching 10 cm^{-1} [4]. Comparison with Fig. 5 shows that in order to match this resolution, we must limit ourselves to a 3.55° deviation from normal incidence.

B. Spectrometer Assembly

The limits on the acceptance angle of the Fabry-Pérot interferometer profoundly affect the assembly of the spectrometer. At each step, we must reverse-propagate the light through the system to ensure that the angle requirements are satisfied. We now consider the issue of the collimating lens and the laser spot size on the SERS substrate. As a size reference, the mirror apertures on the Fabry-Pérot interferometers are $\sim 1 \text{ mm}$ in diameter, corresponding to an aperture radius of $500 \mu\text{m}$. The wavelength of light that we are working with is sufficiently large that diffraction effects can be neglected, and provided that we choose a collimating lens of sufficiently large diameter ($\gtrsim 1 \text{ cm}$), the paraxial approximation holds and ray-tracing methods can be used to analyze the system.

We show in Fig. 8 the ray-tracing diagram used to characterize the propagation of the critical rays through a lens

of refractive index n . As can be seen from inspection, the highest angular deviation will arise from the ray propagating from the image r (*i.e.*, one edge of the laser spot) to the point h (*i.e.*, the aperture edge 180° opposite). Note that while there is a small horizontal offset between the entrance and exit points on the lens, this distance is much smaller than the dimensions of the system and is therefore neglected. Similarly, the lens is placed in close proximity to the entrance aperture, so walk-off effects due to the nonzero exit angle γ can be neglected.

Figure 8. Ray tracing diagram of the exit angle γ as a function of finite spot size, substrate-lens separation, and acceptance aperture h .

Assuming (in the paraxial approximation) that all rays which originate from the focal point are collimated, we can find a relationship between the exit angle γ and the spot size and substrate-lens distance (assuming a fixed aperture size h). We chose to use standard 1 inch diameter silica lenses – while true that silicon is transparent in this wavelength range and its greater refractive index would enable us to reduce the form factor, silica greatly reduces reflection losses, obviating the need for antireflective coatings.

The results of the ray-tracing are shown in Fig. 9. Using a silica lens ($n=1.443$ at 1550 nm), we can calculate the resulting value of γ for a range of laser spot sizes and substrate-lens separations. The shaded region corresponds to angles which meet the resolution requirements, and the X marks the parameters chosen for the current design.

It is evident that we could meet the resolution requirements using a smaller separation, further reducing the form factor of the spectrometer. However, it is advantageous to maximize the spot size, in order to have the highest likelihood of exciting an adsorbed analyte molecule.

Figure 9. Dependence of exit angle γ on focal length and spot size for a fused silica lens with entrance aperture $500 \mu\text{m}$.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

SSC Pacific designed and developed the technology to implement a micro electromechanical system (MEMS) based Raman spectrometer operating at 1525 nm , with a small ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^3$) form factor and resolution performance on par with handheld Raman spectrometers. The current iteration, however, is not optimized for Raman spectroscopy – the fundamental physics of both Raman activity and the SERS effect lend themselves to a higher-frequency regime. The characterization and study of the current spectrometer will provide the insight necessary to scale the device down to operate at a more conventional NIR Raman wavelength, which is the next step planned for the MEMS Raman spectrometer.

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